

Factors Associated With Knowledge and Attitudes toward Electronic Cigarettes among Undergraduate Students at a University in Thailand: A Cross-Sectional Study

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Abstract

Background: Currently, the use of electronic cigarettes (e-cigarettes) is becoming increasingly popular worldwide among young people, including in Thailand. The myth of e-cigarette safety has fueled its growing popularity among Thai undergraduates. **Purpose:** This study aimed to investigate factors associated with knowledge and attitudes toward e-cigarettes among undergraduate students at a university in Thailand. **Methods:** This cross-sectional study was conducted between December 2023 and March 2024 among 384 undergraduate students at a university in Thailand. The data on demographics, knowledge, and attitudes toward e-cigarettes were collected using self-administered questionnaires via Google Forms. Descriptive statistics were used to report percentages and frequencies, while binary logistic regression analyses were used to determine associations using STATA 14. **Results:** Of the 384 respondents, 28.40% were current smokers, and 76.80% had never received knowledge about e-cigarettes. Logistic regression analysis revealed that females had better knowledge about e-cigarettes than males. (OR=2.22; 95%CI: 1.29-3.82; P<0.004). Additionally, a history of receiving knowledge about e-cigarettes (OR=1.92; 95%CI: 1.00-3.62; P<0.049) was associated with better knowledge about e-cigarettes. Importantly, having divorced or separated parents (OR= 3.92; 95% CI: 1.91-8.04; P<0.001) was associated with more attitudes toward e-cigarettes, whereas undergraduate students living in private accommodation (OR= 0.36; 95% CI: 0.19-0.69; P<0.002), living at house (OR= 0.13; 95% CI: 0.04-0.47; P<0.002), and current smokers of e-cigarettes (OR= 0.21; 95% CI: 0.09-0.48; P<0.001) had less attitudes about e-cigarettes. **Conclusions:** E-cigarette use is widespread among Thai undergraduate students. These findings highlight the need for university health education to correct misconceptions and raise awareness about the risks and legal bans on e-cigarettes. Strengthening enforcement and peer-led interventions may further curb their use among undergraduate students in Thailand.

Keywords: E-cigarettes, Knowledge, Attitude, Undergraduate Students, Thailand.

INTRODUCTION

Currently, the use of electronic cigarettes (e-cigarettes) is becoming increasingly popular worldwide [1,2,3], with approximately 86 million users globally [4]. This trend is particularly evident among young people [5]. The prevalence of e-cigarette use is 24% among college students in Saudi Arabia [5], 19.7% among university students in Palestine [6], 40.5% in New Zealand [7], and 29.8%

in China [8]. In Thailand, a cross-sectional study of 507 undergraduate students found that the prevalence of e-cigarettes was 12.2% [9].

The factors contributing to the popularity of e-cigarettes stem from advertising strategies that use persuasive messages and selling points similar to those of traditional cigarettes [3], such as enhancing sexual appeal and improving mood [10]. These psychological influences lead users to develop strong beliefs in these perceived benefits, reinforcing their smoking behavior over time. Moreover, e-cigarette advertisements emphasize advantages over traditional cigarettes, such as a wider variety of flavors, being perceived as healthier, having a modern and diverse appearance, and being odor-free. These selling points naturally attract users and increase the likelihood of addiction [11].

With the increasing popularity of e-cigarettes, proponents often claim they are a safer alternative to traditional cigarettes. Consequently, many undergraduate students hold misconceptions and possess inaccurate knowledge and attitudes regarding e-cigarette use [6]. In reality, e-cigarettes are considered equally harmful as traditional cigarettes due to their chemical composition. The aerosol produced during vaping contains numerous hazardous substances, posing significant health risks to both users and those exposed to secondhand emissions. Prolonged inhalation of these aerosols has been associated with respiratory and neurological disorders [12]. Specifically, e-cigarette aerosol contains nicotine, propylene glycol, flavoring agents, carcinogens, and heavy metals such as aluminum, lead, mercury, and zinc. It also includes harmful compounds like carbonyls, epoxides, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, pesticides, and other toxic chemicals [13, 14]. These components collectively contribute to the adverse health effects associated with e-cigarette use [15].

E-cigarettes are currently banned in over 30 countries, including Thailand. In other regions, they are variously regulated as consumer products, pharmaceutical products, tobacco products, placed in different categories, or remain entirely unregulated. The World Health Organization (WHO) strongly supports Thailand's ban on the importation and sale of e-cigarettes, recognizing it as a significant step toward protecting public health especially among youth, and fulfilling the country's obligations under the WHO Framework Convention on Tobacco Control [16]. Despite this, youth aged 15-20 in rural Thailand have demonstrated relatively high levels of knowledge about e-cigarettes and tend to hold positive attitudes regarding their health impacts and legal status. Notably, no significant association was found between perceptions and health-related attitudes. These findings highlight the importance of implementing targeted strategies to correct misperceptions and enhance awareness of the health risks associated with e-cigarette use among rural youth [17].

Despite the growing global trend of e-cigarette use and the significant rise in vaping prevalence in recent years, there remains a lack of information and data on users' knowledge and attitudes, particularly among undergraduate students in Thailand. Understanding their knowledge and attitudes toward e-cigarettes is essential for enhancing e-cigarette control strategies. Therefore, this study aims to investigate factors associated with knowledge and attitudes toward e-cigarettes among undergraduate students in Thailand.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study design and population

A descriptive cross-sectional study investigated factors associated with knowledge and attitudes toward e-cigarettes among undergraduate students at a university in Roi Et Province.

The target population comprised 4,356 undergraduate students enrolled in the regular program for the academic year 2023 at a university in Roi Et Province. The sample size was determined using

Krejcie and Morgan's formula [18], yielding a required sample of 353 participants. To account for potential missing or incomplete responses during data collection, the sample size was increased by 10%, resulting in a final sample of 388 participants. A multistage sampling technique was employed. First, faculties were selected using stratified random sampling, and the sample size for each faculty was calculated based on probability proportional to size. Then, within each selected faculty, undergraduate students were chosen through simple random sampling to complete the questionnaire. The inclusion criteria were: (1) being an undergraduate student, and (2) currently enrolled in the regular program for the academic year 2023 at a university in Roi Et Province in Thailand. The exclusion criterion was unwillingness to participate in the study.

Data Collection

Data were collected using a self-administered questionnaire distributed via Google Forms between December 2023 and March 2024. The researchers held briefing sessions with participants to explain the questionnaire completion process, provide details on response methods, and obtain informed consent. Participants were allotted 20-30 minutes to complete the questionnaire, and researchers monitored the process to ensure that the required sample size was achieved.

Measurements

The questionnaire consisted of three sections.

The first section assessed sociodemographic characteristics using a checklist that included questions on gender, age, faculty, academic year, living conditions, parents' marital status, and monthly living expenses. Additionally, participants were asked about their familiarity with e-cigarettes through the following questions: "How did you get familiar with e-cigarettes?", "Have you ever received knowledge about e-cigarettes?", and "Do you currently smoke?".

The second section was a knowledge questionnaire [19], consisting of 20 items. Participants were asked to identify each item as correct or incorrect regarding knowledge of e-cigarettes. The questionnaire included both positively and negatively worded items, with scores for negative items reversed. Total scores were categorized into two levels: scores of 16-20 ($\geq 80\%$) indicated a good knowledge level, while scores of 0-15 ($< 80\%$) indicated a poor knowledge level. The content validity was evaluated by three experts in e-cigarette research, achieving an index of item objective congruence (IOC) score of 0.67. A pilot test was conducted with 30 individuals similar to the sample group and reliability was tested using Kuder-Richardson 20 (KR-20) Method, yielding a value of 0.68 [19].

The third section was the attitudes questionnaire [19], which consisted of 30 structured items used to assess participants' attitudes toward e-cigarettes. Each item was rated on a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 (absolutely disagree) to 5 (absolutely agree). The questionnaire included both positively and negatively worded items, with the scores for negative items reversed. A higher total score indicated more positive and supportive attitudes toward e-cigarettes. Scores were categorized into two levels: scores ranging from 150 to 200 ($\geq 80\%$) indicated a good attitude level, while scores from 30 to 149 ($< 80\%$) indicated a poor attitude level. The content validity was evaluated by three experts in e-cigarette research, achieving an index of item objective congruence (IOC) score of 0.57. A pilot test was conducted with 30 individuals similar to the sample group and reliability was tested using Cronbach's alpha, yielding a value of 0.89 [19].

Statistical analyses

Data analysis was performed using MS Excel 2013 to extract web-based data from the Google spreadsheet, where cleaning, storing, and coding were performed to simplify the data analysis.

Statistical analysis was performed using STATA 14. Of the 388 participants who were approached, 384 completed the questionnaire. A total of 384 responses were included in the analysis. Descriptive analysis was performed by calculating the frequency and percentages. Binary logistic regression analysis was performed to determine the statistical association among variables. A p-value <0.05 indicated a statistically significant difference.

Ethical Considerations

This study received Ethical approval from the Research Ethics Committee of Roi Et Rajabhat University (Approval number 100/2566).

RESULTS

Table 1: Sociodemographic characteristics (n=384)

Characteristics	Frequency (%)
Gender	
Males	115 (29.90)
Females	269 (70.10)
Age	
≤ 20	165 (43.00)
≥ 21	219 (57.00)
Faculty	
Nursing	30 (7.80)
Information Technology	7 (1.80)
Business Administration and Accountancy	37 (9.60)
Law and Politics	31 (8.10)
Education and Human Development	205 (53.40)
Liberal Arts and Science	74 (19.30)
Academic Year	
Freshman	140 (36.50)
Sophomore	93 (24.20)
Junior	91 (23.70)
Senior	60 (15.60)
Living Conditions	
University accommodation	57 (14.80)
Private accommodation	279 (72.70)
House	48 (12.50)
Parents' Marital Status	
Married	257 (66.90)
Divorced/Separated	53 (13.80)
Father and/or Mother deceased	74 (19.30)
Monthly Living Expenses	
≤ 3,000 baht	82 (21.40)
3,001- 5,000 baht	149 (38.80)
≥5,001baht	153 (39.80)
How did you get familiar with e-cigarettes?	
Family	8 (2.10)
Friends/ Other acquaintances	376 (97.90)
Have you ever received knowledge about e-cigarettes?	
No	295 (76.80)
Yes	89 (23.20)
Do you smoke e-cigarettes?	
No	275 (71.60)
Yes	109 (28.40)

A total of 384 participants were enrolled in this study. Among undergraduate students, 29.90% were male, while 70.10% were female. The majority of participants (57.00%) were 21 years old or older. More than half of the participants (53.40%) were from the Faculty of Education and Human Development, with the largest proportion (36.50%) being freshmen.

Most participants (72.70%) lived in private accommodations, and 66.90% reported that their parents were married. Regarding monthly income, the majority (39.80%) received 5,001 baht or more. Notably, most students (97.90%) became familiar with e-cigarettes through friends or other acquaintances.

However, 76.70% had never received knowledge about e-cigarettes. When asked about their smoking habits, 71.60% stated that they had never smoked e-cigarettes. (Table 1)

Table 2: Binary logistic regression of Knowledge about E-Cigarettes (N=384)

Factors	Knowledge about E-Cigarettes			
	Univariate Regression		Multivariate Regression	
	OR (95% CI)	P-value	OR (95% CI)	P-value
Gender				
Males	Ref.		Ref.	
Females	2.70(1.68-4.32)	<0.001	2.22(1.29-3.82)	0.004*
Age				
≤ 20	Ref.			
≥ 21	1.17(0.74-1.83)	0.488		
Academic Year		0.163		0.032*
Freshman	Ref.		Ref.	
Sophomore	0.57(0.32-1.02)	0.060	0.51(0.27-0.99)	0.048*
Junior	0.88(0.48-1.60)	0.675	0.69(0.35-1.39)	0.309
Senior	1.20(0.58-2.48)	0.613	1.72(0.74-3.95)	0.201
Living Conditions		<0.001		0.002*
University accommodation	Ref.		Ref.	
Private accommodation	0.36(0.15-0.84)	0.018	0.54(0.22-1.35)	0.194
House	0.15(0.05-0.40)	<0.001	0.17(0.06-0.51)	0.002*
Parents' Marital Status		0.005		0.004*
Married	Ref.		Ref.	
Divorced/Separated	1.26(0.61-2.60)	0.522	2.06(0.92-4.59)	0.075
Father and/or Mother deceased	0.43(0.25-0.74)	0.003	0.48(0.26-0.89)	0.021*
Monthly Living Expenses		0.699		
≤ 3,000 baht	Ref.			
3,001-5,000 baht	0.76(0.41-1.42)	0.404		
≥ 5,001baht	0.82(0.44-1.52)	0.540		
How did you get familiar with e-cigarettes?		0.854		
Family	Ref.			
Friends/ Other acquaintances	0.86(0.17-4.33)	0.854		
Have you ever received knowledge about e-cigarettes?		<0.001		<0.001**
No	Ref.		Ref.	
Yes	1.85(1.03-3.33)	0.037	1.92(1.00-3.62)	0.049*
Do you smoke e-cigarettes?		<0.001		<0.001**
No	Ref.			
Yes	0.24(0.15-0.39)	<0.001	0.29(0.17-0.49)	<0.001**

*p < .05 **p < .001, Constant value = 18.009, Pseudo R² (Nagelkerke R²) = 0.167

Abbreviations: OR, odds ratio; CI, confidence interval; Ref., Reference

Table 2 presents the results of the univariate and multivariate logistic regression analyses. The analysis revealed that female participants had significantly higher knowledge about e-cigarettes compared to males (OR = 2.22; 95% CI: 1.29-3.82). Additionally, having a history of receiving knowledge about e-cigarettes was positively associated with higher knowledge levels (OR = 1.92; 95% CI: 1.00-3.62). In contrast, lower knowledge scores were observed among sophomore students (OR = 0.51; 95% CI: 0.27-0.99), those living in houses (OR = 0.17; 95% CI: 0.06-0.51), individuals with deceased parents (OR = 0.48; 95% CI: 0.26-0.89), and current e-cigarette users (OR = 0.29; 95% CI: 0.17-0.49).

Table 3: Binary logistic regression of Attitudes about E-Cigarettes (N=384)

Factors	Attitudes about E-Cigarettes			
	Univariate Regression		Multivariate Regression	
	OR (95% CI)	P-value	OR (95% CI)	P-value
Gender				
Males	Ref.			
Females	1.30(0.74-2.29)	0.347		
Age				
≤ 20	Ref.			
≥ 21	0.65(0.39-1.08)	0.098		
Academic Year		0.189		
Freshman	Ref.			
Sophomore	0.64(0.33-1.23)			
Junior	0.66(0.34-1.27)			
Senior	0.44(0.19-1.02)			
Living Conditions		<0.001		<0.001*
University accommodation	Ref.		Ref.	
Private accommodation	0.36(0.19-0.67)	0.001	0.36(0.19-0.69)	0.002
House	0.14(0.04-0.45)	0.001	0.13(0.04-0.47)	0.002
Parents' Marital Status		0.012		
Married	Ref.		Ref.	
Divorced/Separated	2.43(1.27-4.62)	0.007	3.92(1.91-8.04)	<0.001**
Father and/or Mother deceased	0.76(0.37-1.55)	0.451	1.04(0.49-2.23)	0.899
Monthly Living Expenses		0.163		
≤ 3,000 baht	Ref.			
3,001- 5,000 baht	1.69(0.80-3.58)	0.167		
≥5,001baht	1.98(0.95-4.14)	0.068		
How did you get familiar with e-cigarettes?				
Family	Ref.			
Friends/ Other acquaintances	1.80(0.21-14.87)	0.557		
Have you ever received knowledge about e-cigarettes?				
No	Ref.			
Yes	0.99(0.55-1.79)	0.981		
Do you smoke e-cigarettes?		<0.001		<0.001*
No	Ref.		Ref.	
Yes	0.23(0.10-0.50)	<0.001	0.21(0.09-0.48)	<0.001*

*p < .05 **p < .001, Constant value = 18.009, Pseudo R² (Nagelkerke R²) = 0.167

Abbreviations: OR, odds ratio; CI, confidence interval; Ref., Reference

Table 3 presents the results of the univariate and multivariate logistic regression analyses. The findings indicate that undergraduate students with divorced or separated parents had significantly higher attitude scores toward e-cigarettes (OR = 3.92; 95% CI: 1.91-8.04). In contrast, participants living in private accommodations (OR = 0.36; 95% CI: 0.19-0.69), living in houses (OR = 0.13; 95% CI: 0.04-0.47), and current e-cigarette use (OR = 0.21; 95% CI: 0.09-0.48) demonstrated significantly lower attitudes scores toward e-cigarettes.

DISCUSSION

This study aimed to explore the factors associated with knowledge and attitudes toward e-cigarettes among undergraduate students at a university in Thailand. Among the 384 undergraduate students, 28.40% were smokers, and 76.80% had never received any knowledge about e-cigarettes. Several demographic and contextual factors were significantly associated with these outcomes.

The findings of this study revealed that female participants possessed significantly higher knowledge about e-cigarettes than males. This may be attributed to greater health awareness among females and a stronger interest in understanding the health effects of e-cigarettes. These results are consistent with studies conducted in Saudi Arabia [20], Bahrain [21], and Palestine [22]. However, they contrast with previous research indicating that males had higher knowledge scores than females [23], which may reflect variations in health information-seeking behaviors or a greater receptiveness to health education campaigns among females.

Additionally, students who had previously received knowledge about e-cigarettes demonstrated significantly higher knowledge levels, supporting existing evidence on the effectiveness of targeted health education programs in improving student knowledge [19]. Interestingly, this study found that sophomore students had significantly lower knowledge levels than freshmen.

This may suggest a need to sustain education efforts beyond the initial years of study, as knowledge may decline or become outdated without reinforcement. Additionally, this study found that undergraduate students living at home or in private accommodations demonstrated lower levels of knowledge compared to those in university dormitories, suggesting that on-campus students may benefit from greater exposure to institutional health promotion activities [7].

Regarding attitudes toward e-cigarettes, undergraduate students with divorced or separated parents exhibited a more positive disposition. This may be attributed to psychological coping mechanisms or altered social dynamics commonly observed in such family environments, which could shape perceptions of smoking behavior [10]. In contrast, current e-cigarette users demonstrated significantly more negative attitudes, a finding consistent with previous research suggesting that users often minimize the perceived health risks of e-cigarettes, potentially due to cognitive dissonance or addiction-related biases [13]. For example, one study found that exclusive e-cigarette users and dual users were significantly more likely than non-users to perceive e-cigarettes as having minimal or no health risks [24]. This study found that undergraduate students living in private accommodations or houses had lower attitudes toward e-cigarettes.

Supporting this, a study in Thailand reported that students in institutional dormitories were significantly more likely to use e-cigarettes than those in private accommodations [25]. Similarly, research in northern Thailand showed that students living at home were less likely to use e-cigarettes than those in dormitories or other housing, suggesting more negative attitudes among those in private living arrangements [26]. This study found that most undergraduate students were introduced to e-cigarettes through peers rather than family or formal sources, highlighting the strong influence of social networks on smoking initiation, as supported by previous research [11].

A systematic review similarly identified peer influence as a key factor in e-cigarette use among adolescents in Southeast Asia [27]. Additionally, a prior study at the Institute of Medicine reported that only 71.5% of undergraduate students who had heard of e-cigarettes demonstrated adequate knowledge [28]. Consistent with these findings, the current study revealed a low percentage of undergraduate students receiving knowledge about e-cigarettes, underscoring the urgent need for comprehensive university-level interventions.

Although e-cigarettes are illegal in Thailand, their use among undergraduate students is widespread, driven by misinformation about their safety. A previous study among Thai university students found that 20.4% had used e-cigarettes, with 40% unaware of their nicotine content. Moreover, 28% believed e-cigarettes help to quit smoking, while 22% were unsure [29]. These findings underscore the urgent need for targeted health literacy campaigns and public health interventions in universities to correct misconceptions and raise awareness of the health risks and legal consequences associated with e-cigarette use [28, 29].

This study has several limitations. First, the sample was drawn from a single university in Northeastern Thailand, limiting the generalizability of the findings to undergraduate students in similar border-area institutions. Additionally, because the university does not distinctly categorize faculties into Health Science and Non-Health Science, placing the Public Health program under the Faculty of Liberal Arts and Sciences, the faculty variable could not be analyzed as a contributing factor. Future research should include more representative samples to enable national generalization and consider adopting a longitudinal design for deeper insights.

CONCLUSION

E-cigarette use is widespread among Thai undergraduate students. Factors such as gender, living conditions, academic year, parental marital status, and smoking history were significantly associated with knowledge and attitude levels. These findings point to the urgent need for university-based health education programs that target misconceptions and promote accurate information about the health risks and legal restrictions associated with e-cigarette use. Strengthening the enforcement of existing bans and promoting peer-based interventions could further reduce the uptake of e-cigarettes among university students in Thailand.

Declaration of Conflicting Interest

All authors declared no potential conflict of interest in the study.

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Authors' Contributions

All authors contributed substantially to the conception and design, acquisition of data, data analysis, and interpretation of data. In addition, all drafted the manuscript or revised it critically for important intellectual content and provided approval of the final version. Data Availability The

dataset generated and analyzed during the current study is available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Declaration of Use of AI in Academic Writing

The authors used Claude AI in the writing process to improve readability and remove grammatical errors.

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